

Speculation on Radiation from a Moving Charge Part II

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It is known that a photon has E and B fields of the same strength (for $c=1$) which are perpendicular to each other. This follows from Maxwell's equations with no sources. In this note, we ask whether one may have such a solution in the case of sources? A solution is the case of an accelerating charge. In usual treatments (1), one begins with the scenario of an accelerating charge and then finds that radiation is emitted. We start with the goal of finding equal strength E and B fields which are perpendicular. Usually, there is an asymmetry between E and B, because E still exists for a particle at rest. With E and B equal ($c=1$), there is no such asymmetry and it seems the E and B fields are free from the charged particle.

In Part I of this note, we considered the electrostatic case for which there is self-energy due to the electric field of $.5\epsilon_0 E^2$ and also an electrostatic potential, q/r . We argued that a second charge q_1 would have an increased mass due to $q_1 q/r$. If the charge q accelerates, one may write ma , where a is acceleration, but this should apply also to q/r i.e. there should be a term qa/r which is related to force i.e. should appear in E. This term drops very slowly with r .

In this note, we consider the idea of a moving charge with the idea of a B field emerging as noted by experiment. Furthermore, there should be an expression:

$$d/dt \text{ energy density} + \text{grad dot } S = 0 \text{ ((1)) (in regions with no source)}$$

((1)) follows from Maxwell's equations, but may be written independently (with energy density and S being unknown). Energy density for $v=0$ is $.5\epsilon_0 E^2$. B emerges only with v (velocity) and so one may speculate that it is linked to momentum. Given that static energy density is of a quadratic form E^2 , one may postulate that S (momentum flux) is also quadratic of the form $[E][B]$. Given that there is a leading term of E in the case of acceleration of aq/r and integrating grad dot S over volume gives S dot dA. The area of a sphere goes as r^2 so S should go as $1/r$ for radiation to be given off. This is equivalent to E and B having the same leading r behaviour i.e. B should go as $1/r$. In fact, for E and B of the same strength (which means that one has lost the dominance of the electrostatic E), it is equivalent to light being emitted. Thus, it seems that the idea of the photon having equal strength ($c=1$) E and B fields perpendicular to each other is present in an accelerating charge system (to leading order). (There are other orders of E and B in such a system which are not associated with radiation.)

Finally, we consider the issues related to particle/wave duality associated with the photon and the continuity equation.

Equal Strength, Perpendicular E and B Fields with Sources

Maxwell's equations may be solved for the case of no sources. One finds $E \exp(ikx - i\omega t)$ and $B \exp(ikx - i\omega t)$ with E and B are perpendicular to each other and to the photon motion and of

equal strength for $c=1$. A question arises: Can one find a solution of equal strength but perpendicular E and B for an EM system with sources i.e. with a charge and current?

The case of charge moving at constant v is well known. There is a B perpendicular to the direction of motion and to E , but E and B strengths are different. B depends linearly on v , so for small v it is very small while E dominates because it is nonzero even if v becomes 0. Thus, there is a distinct asymmetry and there is no equal E , B solution.

Consider the definitions which follow from Maxwell's equations from (1):

$$E = -dA/dt - \text{grad } \phi \quad \text{and} \quad B = \text{grad } \times A \quad ((2))$$

With

$$\phi(r,t) = 1/(4\pi \epsilon_0) \int \text{charge density}(r_1,t_1) / R \, dv_1 \quad ((3))$$

where R is the distance from r_1 where a piece of charge exists to a measuring point r (measured from a fixed origin).

$$A = \mu_0/(4\pi) \int dv_1 J(r_1, t_1) / R \quad ((4))$$

The objective is to find E and B which are perpendicular and of equal strength. A first step is to write:

$$R = |r-r_1| \approx r - r_1 \cdot r/r \quad ((5))$$

It would be good to have a contribution from $\text{grad } \phi$ to E . d/dt acts on the source, so it seems that this would give a leading term as r is untouched in dA/dt . Thus, $-\text{grad } \phi$ should behave in the same way. A way to arrange this is to allow t_1 to depend on t and R in such a way that d/dt and d/dr yield the same result with $c=1$. This leads to the idea of the measurement at R occurring a time R/c after something happens at r_1 or $t_1=t-R/c$. The EM measurement in the field is taken at time t .

Then, using ((5)) one may expand charge density in ((3)). This leads to:

$$\phi(r,t) = 1/(4\pi \epsilon_0) \left\{ q/r + r \cdot p(t-r/c)/(r^3) + r \cdot qv(t-r/c) / (r^2) \right\} \quad ((6))$$

Here p is the dipole moment of the charge. The dipole term drops to rapidly to be of leading order.

Thus: $d/dr \phi = 1/(4\pi \epsilon_0) \left\{ r \cdot qv(t-r/c)/(r^3) - r(\text{vector}) \right\}$. This is of order $1/r$.

From ((4)), dA/dt acts directly on the source also yielding a $1/r$ term i.e. $\mu_0/(4\pi \epsilon_0) qv(t-r/c)$

Lastly, one must calculate $\text{grad } \times A$. As shown in (1):

$$B = (\text{grad } 1/r) \times qv(t-r/c) + 1/r \text{ grad } \times qv(t-r/c) \quad ((7))$$

The second order term drops the least with r and may be shown to be $\text{rvector}/(rr) \times qv(t-r/c)$.

(For example, this may be shown using the determinant form of the cross-product in Cartesian coordinates.)

Thus, B is perpendicular to $qv(t-r/c)$ and hence dA/dt , but also to rvector and so to $-\text{grad } \phi$. Its strength is also the same as E because the various d/dt and grads yield the same result operating on $t-r/c$ for $c=1$.

Thus, insisting that E and B be perpendicular and of the same strength in the presence of sources leads to a solution of an accelerating charge. The idea of equal strength means that there are terms for which E static does not dominate, but E and B are on equal footing, suggesting that they are no longer part of the charge system.

One may integrate ((1)) with $S = 1/\epsilon_0 \int E \times B$ over volume to obtain a surface integral. S goes as $1/(rr)$ and the surface of a sphere as $4\pi r^2$, so there is non-zero flux moving out of the sphere even as it gets larger and larger. This is the idea of radiation moving from a source outward.

Speculation on the Magnetic Field B

In this section, we wish to speculate on the idea of emitted radiation by an accelerating charge and B by only using electrostatic information. In this case, one knows there is an E field of the form kq/r^2 , a self-energy of $.5\epsilon_0 E^2$ and a potential of q/r . In Part I of this note, we argued that if a second charge q_1 is brought near q (and the two held in place), the second charge acquires an EM mass of $q_1 q/r$. If q accelerates, one should have ma and this should apply to all mass so there should be a term associated with force proportional to aq/r . This force should be associated with the electric field.

Furthermore, it is known experimentally that there is a magnetic field, although without Maxwell's equation (except for the static case), one does not know much about it.

One may argue that in general there should be a continuity equation of the form (1). Although such an equation does follow from Maxwell's equations, it may be written a priori except for the fact that one does not know energy density or S . One may note that energy density should be linked to $.5\epsilon_0 E^2$. In fact, it may be $.5\epsilon_0 E^2 + \text{Function}$. Given that E has a leading term of aq/r in the case of an accelerating charge, if B is to have the same strength as E (at least in one term and with $c=1$), then it too should have a term of aq/r . [The reason that E and B should have equal magnitude is that if they are to form radiation there is no further information of the charge system. For E and B fields attached to the charge system there is an asymmetry because E exists for $v=0$. Thus, B which depends on v increases from a small value as v increases.] $\int S \cdot dA$ integrated over a sphere should give a nonzero value. In fact, if Area goes as $4\pi r^2$, then S should go as $1/r^2$. Otherwise, it drops too quickly or grows which would be unphysical. This suggests an $[E][B]$ type of solution for S with $[E]$ and $[B]$ having the same magnitude.

We already noted in part 1 that if E has a term aq/r then this should follow from $-\text{grad } \phi$, but $\phi = \int dv_1 \text{ charge density}(r_1, t_1)/R$ where R is the distance from r_1 to a measuring point r measured from a fixed origin. (r_1 , a vector, is also measured from this fixed origin.) This led to

the idea of $t_1 = t - R/c$ and $R = |r - r_1| = r - r_1 \cdot r/r$. Then performing a Taylor series of charge density $\rho(r_1, t - R/c)$ about t yields a term related to acceleration. Such a term should also appear in dA/dt suggesting $\int dv j(r_1, t - R/c)/r$ as a solution for A , the magnetic potential.

Thus, we argue that using ideas of radiation and equal E and B , together with electrostatics, one may postulate some of the pieces of classical electrodynamics.

Continuity Equation

It is interesting to consider the continuity equation which follows from Maxwell's equations i.e.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E^2 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{\mu_0} B^2 \right\} + \frac{1}{\mu_0} \text{grad} \cdot E \times B = E \cdot j \quad ((8))$$

For the case of a photon, the RHS of ((8)) is 0 and for radiation from accelerating charge one may consider a region where the RHS of ((8)) is 0. For the photon case, one has a solution of $E \exp(ipx - iEt)$ and $B \exp(ipx - iEt)$ with E and B perpendicular (and to the direction of motion) and $p = E/c$. Thus, there is an energy density and momentum flux associated with an specific energy E and momentum p . This has the appearance of particle/wave duality with p and E representing the particle i.e. a hit is associated with the full p , not a piece of a wave, yet there is an energy density suggesting a probability to find the photon particle within a wavelike structure.

For the case of a source (accelerating charge), the symmetry of the charge dominates i.e. one deals with spherical symmetry. Nevertheless, the radiation portions of E and B only involve d/dt or grad operating on $qv(t - r/c)$ and not on $1/r$. Thus, the leading terms do not drop as those "stuck" to the charge. The accelerating source still dominates the solution because its acceleration determines the strength of the radiation emitted. Even though E and B (which have the same strength and are perpendicular) are expressed in terms of $a(t - r/c)$, a solution to ((8)) with the RHS side equal to 0 and E and B of the same strength and perpendicular is $\exp(ikx - iEt)$, so the radiation emitted seems to be consistent with the photon solution, and to particle/wave duality.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the photon solution with E and B perpendicular and of equal strength and ask: Can one find such a solution for a system with a charge present? It seems one may by considering charge density to be a function of $t - R/c$ where t is the time a measurement is made and R the distance from the charge to the measurement point and by considering an accelerating charge. Thus, we argue one may consider finding photons (or radiation) as equivalent to finding E and B perpendicular and of equal strength. It is interesting to note that for a charge at rest, there is only an E field and for small velocities B is small. Thus, there is an asymmetry between E and B . With radiation, no such asymmetry should exist.

We also argue that one may begin with electrostatic ideas and consider a second charge q_1 near q . Q_1 has an extra EM mass of $q_1 q/r$. If q is accelerated, one has ma for all mass so there should be a term associated with E of aq/r . This is a very slowly dropping term. We use this term

together with a continuity equation and equal strength to make predictions about the magnetic field without using Maxwell's equations.

Finally, we note that the continuity equation for a photon represents energy density and momentum flux, but contains $\exp(ipx-iEt)$. This seems to indicate particle/wave duality. The energy density and flux represent a kind of probability distribution, while p and E (equal to each other for $c=1$) indicate a specific energy and p for the photon i.e. a hit with the photon delivers the entire momentum not a piece of the wave (already known by Einstein analyzing the photoelectric effect).

References

1. Reitz, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory 3rd edition (Addison-Wesley 1980)